

SAROJINI NAIDU

GOVERNMENT GIRLS POST GRADUATE AUTONOMOUS COLLEGE
SHIVAJI NAGAR BHOPAL - 462016 M.P. INDIA

QUALITY ASSURANCE CELL

a quest for excellence

One Week Training Program on
QUALITY SUSTENANCE & FACULTY DEVELOPMENT

SAROJINI NAIDU

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Dr. VANDANA AGNIHOTRI
Chairperson - IQAC

Dr. H.K. GARG
Director - IQAC

Dr. VEENA DANI
Co-coordinator - IQAC

Dr. Bharti Jain
Dr. G.P. Yadav
Dr. Mamta Maheshwari
Dr. Kiran Sharma
Dr. Pratishtha Khare
Dr. Kusum Mathur
Dr. Ruchira Chowdhary
Dr. Indira Javed
Dr. Rohit Trivedi

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One Week Training Program on

QUALITY SUSTENANCE & FACULTY DEVELOPMENT

ONE WEEK TRAINING ON QUALITY SUSTENANCE & FACULTY DEVELOPMENT 2016*11*16-21

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Itinerary

Day - 1 2015/11/16

INAUGURATION	Value Education Vs Quality Education	A Quest for Excellence
Coordinator's Address Dr. H.K Garg	Shri S.C. Behar Former Chief Secretary Govt. of M.P.	Dr. H.K. Garg Director, IQAC Coordinator, Steering Committee
Principal's Speech Dr. Vandana Agnihotri		

Day - 2 2015/11/17

Quality Culture in HE : Concept & Assessment	Alzheimer's : A Disease of 21 st Century	Inclusive Education
Dr. Pramila Maini Former Director, IEHE Ex-Member, EC NAAC	Dr. Veena Dani Professor of Psychology	Mrs. Kala Mohan Educational Management Consultant & Child Counselor

Day - 3 2015/11/18

Quality Challenges & Sustenance	Store Purchase Rules, 2015	Striving for Excellence
Dr. Shashi Rai Member, State HE Council Ex- Member UGC, NAAC	Mrs. Veena Bhanupriya Former Additional Director Dept. of Finance, M.P.	Mr. I.S. Dani Former Addl. Chief Secretary, M.P. Chairman, Land Reforms

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Itinerary

Day - 4 2015/11/19

Quest for Peace & Happiness	RUN BHOPAL RUN (A Health & Sanitary Awareness Event involving 10,000 natives)
Mr. Rajesh Jagesiya Trainer cum Facilitator The Art of Living, Bengaluru	Collector Bhopal District, Bhopal

Day - 5 2015/11/20

Balanced Diet In Indian Context	Self Appraisal for PBAS & CAS	Green Research : Prospects & Perspectives
Mrs. Amita Singh Expert, Nutrition & Dietetics	Dr. Bharti Jain Professor of Chemistry	Dr. Moni Mathur Retired Professor of Botany

Day - 6 2015/11/21

Making Money with Joy	Investment : Pros & Cons	VALEDICTORY
Mr. Pradeep Karambelkar Investment Advisor	Mr. L.D. Pandit Ex Manager M.P. Coop Bank	IQAC Team

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Coordinator's Address

Higher Education has witnessed turbulent changes over the last few decades. On one side is the mushrooming of colleges at every nook of the city, churning out unfinished graduates, on the other side there has been a steady decline in the educational standards, where academics and values both seems to have taken a back seat.

On a globe, where ICT offers all advanced tools like teleconferencing, e-mail, audio-learning, television classes, interactive voice response system, webinars, etc., to the potential scholars, our undergraduates are still relying on hard copies of notes or exam-ready booklets for easy scores.

The collegiate education system is amazingly stringent and inimical to change. Firstly, the academic decisions are taken at political level and slapped on the educational guild. Secondly, the over-enthusiastic administration is always on-toes to implement the action plan at once, without sensitizing the academic executors & stakeholders. To this, quality initiatives are never roused from within the system; when introduced from outside, they are resisted; if imposed, they are ritualized. Therefore, most of the innovations succumb at the very embryonic stage.

We strongly feel that there is an urgent need of active participation from teachers, learners and the society, at large, to express their aptitude and insight with unclouded thoughts and self-awareness. With this framework in mind, the Quality Assurance Cell has organized a One week Capacity Building Program on **Quality Sustenance & Faculty Development**. The program has been meticulously customized to let the faculty manage their personal, academic, intellectual and fiscal portfolio besides delivering quality in their daily academic and executive pursuits. The upcoming week shall be peppered with a series of Guest Lectures, Group Discussions and Brainstorming Sessions on diverse topics to cherish the veteran minds. Hope the program would bring productive outcome.

Dr. H.K. GARG

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अध्यक्षीय उद्बोधन

प्रिय साथियों

महाविद्यालय के आंतरिक गुणवत्ता आश्वासन प्रकोष्ठ द्वारा आयोजित एक सप्ताह के प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम में आप सभी का स्वागत है। सरोजिनी नायडू शासकीय कन्या महाविद्यालय की गणना मध्यप्रदेश के अत्यंत प्रतिष्ठित महाविद्यालयों में की जाती है। एक सप्ताह की अवधि के लिए आयोजित यह प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम संस्था के गुणात्मक विकास और अकादमिक उन्नति में अभिवृद्धि करेगा ऐसा मुझे पूरा विश्वास है।

मैं अपने सेवाकाल में अनेक महाविद्यालयों में पदस्थ रही हूँ किन्तु यह प्रथम अवसर है जब मैंने इस प्रकार के स्ववित्तीय कार्यक्रम का आयोजन देखा है। मैं आपके इस कदम की सराहना करती हूँ और उम्मीद करती हूँ कि आप इसमें अपनी नियमित रूप से सहभागिता कर इसे सार्थक बनाएंगे।

हमें शिक्षण के क्षेत्र में सूचना प्रौद्योगिकी का समावेश तथा नव-प्रवर्तन करने होंगे। जब तक हम अपनी छात्राओं को नवीन शिक्षण पद्धतियों से रू-ब-रू नहीं करायेंगे तब तक हमारी छात्राएं पूर्ण रूप से दक्ष नहीं हो सकती। इसी अनुक्रम में आंतरिक गुणवत्ता आश्वासन प्रकोष्ठ द्वारा एक समय सारिणी तैयार की गई है। सभी विभाग उक्त सारिणी के अनुसार आगामी सेमेस्टर से प्रत्येक सप्ताह कम में कम एक व्याख्यान स्मार्ट क्लास रूम में अवश्य लें।

हमारा प्रयास हो कि हम महाविद्यालय के अकादमिक, शोध तथा प्रशासनिक वातावरण को सरल व सहभागितापूर्ण बनायें। आंतरिक गुणवत्ता आश्वासन प्रकोष्ठ द्वारा आयोजित वर्तमान प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम इसी दिशा में एक सकारात्मक कदम है। मुझे विश्वास है कि हम सभी के समन्वित प्रयासों से महाविद्यालय के सर्वांगीण विकास की ओर यह एक सार्थक पहल सिद्ध होगी।

कार्यक्रम के सफलता की शुभकामनाओं के साथ –

डॉ. वंदना अग्निहोत्री

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Mr. S.C. Behar IAS, is the Former Chief Secretary of Madhya Pradesh.

A Philanthropist by nature and Academician by heart, Mr. Behar served the state in various capacities. As Principal Secretary, Higher Education, he was a harbinger of change in Collegiate Education of the state.

He has large number of reforms to his credit, which includes 1984 Education Policy, Maintenance of Teachers' Diary & Attendance Register, Concept of Model Colleges, Grant of Autonomy to Government Colleges in M.P., etc.

Quality Education vs Value Education

S.C. Behar

Former Chief Secretary, Madhya Pradesh

- Knowledge is virtue.
- Education is a tool of social transformation
- Academic excellence and honesty need to be harmonized.
- A good education system has to find out questions, not the answers.
- Preference is to be given to symbiosis and not to competition or antagonism.
- Examinations in autonomous colleges should be unsupervised.
- Value system needs to be augmented.
- The present system is a masquerade where people assume progress but literally they are oppressed.
- Education system should be comprehended in a correct manner.
- All knowledge systems should be explored and understood.
- Real learning in our education system will improve the knowledge of our young generation.

ONE WEEK TRAINING ON QUALITY SUSTENANCE & FACULTY DEVELOPMENT 2016*11*16-21

A Quest for Excellence

Dr. H.K. GARG

Director, IQAC ; Coordinator, Steering Committee

DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITY CULTURE

- Construction of bench marks through conscious, catalytic & consistent efforts.
- Enhancement in the academic & administrative performance of the institution.
- Promotion of Quality Circle (through Conferences, Webinars, Workshops).
- Creation of learner-centric environment.
- Adoption of interactive & participatory teaching - learning methods.
- Preference to innovative & entrepreneurial approaches.
- Amalgamation of competent learning & Skills.
- Inculcation of value system.
- Orientation of faculty towards more & more use of IT.
- Consolidation of management information system (MIS).
- Promotion of interdisciplinary research.
- Networking in neighborhood.

- Linkages & collaborations with equals & others.
- Institutionalization of best practices.
- Recognition as a harbinger of change.
- Development of a strong feedback mechanism from all stakeholders (Students, Parents, Hostellers, Alumni, Society, Employer, Teachers of eminence, etc.)

SEVEN CRITERIA OF ASSESSMENT

Curricular Aspects

Curriculum supplemented, enriched or redesigned :

- As per freedom allowed ;
- In analogy to the institutional mission ;
- Wide range of elective options/courses ;
- Consistent with emerging global & national present-day needs ;
- Flexibility in time frame ;
- Horizontal & vertical mobility ;
- Additional enrichment programs

Dr. H.K.GARG did his post graduate studies in Zoology, securing highest marks in the University.

Having started his career with All India Radio as Anchor, his passion to touch the sky tempted him to join the Civil Aviation as Apprentice Pilot and, later on, the Indian Air Force as Pilot Officer, but his scholastic bent of mind pulled him back into academics.

He has published a Book on Research Techniques in Molecular Biology, Genetics & Biotechnology (LAP Germany), ±100 popular articles and ≥80 Research Papers in Souvenirs & Indexed Journals of National & International acclaim with a Global Impact Factor of 29.117.

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Feedback on Curriculum

- From experts & stakeholders on the relevance of contents ; and
- to customize as per personal and professional requirement of students.

Teaching, Learning & Evaluation Admission

- Well ordered & transparent ;
- Conform to the norms of state government (regulatory body) ;
- Equity and wide access to all socio-economic sections, gender and differently-abled students.

Teacher's Quality

- Faculty qualification ;
- Stay & availability ;
- Knowledge of recent updates ;
- Innovations & improvements in teaching
- Use of interactive instructional techniques ;
- High order thinking ;
- Engagement in research & investigation.

Teaching Modalities

- Assignment/ experiments through ICT ;
- Interviews ;
- Focused group discussion ;
- Debates & extempore ;
- Projects ;
- Presentations ;
- Practicum ;
- Surveys.

Interactive & Participatory Methods of Learning

- Responsibility in learning ;
- Process of construction of knowledge.

Strategies to cater the needs of students from diverse background

Evaluation

- Assistance in improving the competence of students ; and
- Assessment of knowledge and skills at various levels ;
- Demarcation of areas where the students have done fairly well and where improvement is required ;
- Indication of areas where learning has happened and/ or the skills have been acquired.

Research, Consultancy and Extension

Policies with reference to research, consultancy and extension :

- Efforts made by the institution to promote research culture ;
- Support mechanism to enable faculty as well as scholar to submit research proposals and to approach funding agencies -
- * flexibility in administrative process ; and
- * academic & infrastructural support.

Practices

- Interdepartmental and interdisciplinary research activities ;

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- Collaborations with other HEI/ research bodies for :
 - * Training ;
 - * Students & faculty exchange ; and
 - * Research & resource sharing.

Outcome

- Research publications & awards ;
- Consultancy incentive ;
- Process & strategies that sensitize students to the social concerns ;
- Institutional Social Responsibility through extension activities on :
 - * Community issues ;
 - * Gender disparity ; and
 - * Social inequity.

Infrastructure and Learning Resources

- **ADEQUACY AND OPTIMAL USE OF AVAILABLE RESOURCES**
- Adequate facilities for prevailing courses
- All constituents - students, teachers, staff, everyone has an access and gets benefitted ;
- Library holds books, journals & e-material in sufficiency to acquire skills, knowledge and other information ;
- Proper deployment of technical staff/ operators ;
- Ample use of ICT and open access by staff & students.

Campus Maintenance

- Supportive facilities are available for curricular, extra-curricular and administrative activities ;
- Regular upkeep of infrastructure ;
- Allocation of funds for maintenance and proper utilization of resources.

Students Supports and Progression

- Institution's concern for students progression :
 - * incremental growth or optimal

progression ;

- * ensure vertical movement ;
- * move to higher levels in education ; and
- * fetch a gainful employment.

Students participation in :

- Social responsibilities ;
 - Cultural activities ; and
 - Leisure activities ;
- for holistic development

Facilitating Mechanisms

- Career Guidance Cell ;
- Placement Cell ;
- Grievance Redressal Cell ;
- Counseling System.

Governance, Leadership & Management

- Coordination between Academic and Administrative Strategies ;
- Establishment of Values ;
- Unclouded Vision and Mission ;
- Formulation of Ideas, Objectives, Directives, Guidelines and Plans for implementation ;
- Planning and Deployment of Human Resources ;

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- Participative decision & Team work ;
- Systematization, Transparency & Justice ;
- Capability to upgrade Faculty Competence ;
- Performance Appraisal & Feedback ;
- Analysis of Response ;
- Strategies for Mobilizing Resources ;
- Budgeting, Optimum Planning ; and Allocation of Financial Resources
- Probity in Public Finance.

Innovation and Best Practices

- Innovative efforts for excellence ;
- Visible impact on Academic and Administrative Quality.

भंडार क्रय नियम 2015

श्रीमती वीणा भानुप्रिया

पूर्व अतिरिक्त संचालक, वित्त विभाग, म.प्र. शासन

- रूपए 15,000.00 तक बिना निविदा सामग्री क्रय की जा सकती है.
- विभागीय क्रय समिति द्वारा रूपए 15,000.00 से 100,000.00 तक क्रय किया जा सकता है.
- रूपए 100,000.00 से 500,000.00 तक की सामग्री, सीमित निविदा के माध्यम से क्रय की जा सकती है.
- रूपए 500,000.00 से अधिक हेतु खुली निविदाएं आमंत्रित करनी होंगी.
- क्रय प्रक्रिया में स्थानीय और म.प्र. शासन के पंजीकृत निकायों को प्राथमिकता दी जायेगी.
- विशेष परिस्थितियों में सक्षम प्रशासनिक अनुमति से राज्य के बाहर से भी सामग्री क्रय की जा सकती है.
- कार्यालय चाहे तो e- निविदा के माध्यम से भी क्रय कर सकते हैं.

Mrs. Veena Bhanupriya has been Additional Director in Department of Finance, Tribal Welfare, Women & Child Development.

Having served for 37 years, she was retired from State Administrative Services in 2014. She has also served as Financial Advisor with Barkatullah University Bhopal.

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Quality Culture in Higher Education Concept & Assessment

Dr. Pramila Maini

Former Director, Institute of Excellence in Higher Education

QUALITY CONCEPT

- * Q - Quest for excellence
- * U - Understanding the concept
- * A - Action oriented
- * L - Learner continue approach
- * I - Innovation for change
- * T - Training to building competencies.
- * Y - Year round activities

- Quality is a philosophy; it's a journey and it's all what we practice
- Quality has a four central ideas around which the whole concept revolves :
 - * Quality as inclusiveness ;
 - * Quality as relativity ;
 - * Quality as process ; and
 - * Quality as culture.

NEED FOR QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

- Growing competition.
- Customer satisfaction.
- To improve employees' morale.
- Maintaining standards as well as image of institution.
- Globalization of education.

WEIGHTAGE TO SEVEN CRITERIA OF ASSESSMENT

Criterion		Score
1	Curricular Aspects	Curricular Planning & Implementation
		Academic Flexibility
		Curriculum Enrichment
		Feedback System
		Total
		150

Dr. Pramila Maini has 44 years of teaching, research and academic experience. She served as Deputy Secretary, Dept. of Higher Education, Govt. of MP., Joint Director, Directorate of Higher Education, MP and Director, IEHE.

She has been a member of General Council & Executive Committee of NAAC.

Dr. Maini has guided 12 Scholars for Ph.D.; published/contributed more than 60 Research Papers in Journals/ Conferences including those held at BARC Trombay, American Chemical Society, Washington, USA etc.

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Criterion		Score	
2	Teaching Learning & Evaluation	Student Enrolment and Profile	30
		Catering to Student Diversity	40
		Teaching-Learning Process	100
		Teacher Quality	60
		Evaluation Process & Reforms	30
		Student Performance and Learning Outcomes	40
		Total	300

Criterion		Score	
3	Research Consultancy & Extension	Promotion of Research	20
		Resource Mobilization for Research	20
		Research Facilities	20
		Research Publications and Awards	20
		Consultancy	10
		Extension Activities and Institutional Social Responsibility	50
		Collaborations	10
Total	150		
4	Research Consultancy & Extension	Physical Facilities	30
		Library as a Learning Resource	20
		IT Infrastructure	30
		Maintenance of Campus Facilities	20
		Total	100

Criterion		Score	
5	Student Support & Progression	Student Mentoring and Support	40
		Student Progression	40
		Students Participation and Activities	20
		Total	100
		6	Governance, Leadership & Management
Strategy Development & Deployment	10		
Faculty Empowerment Strategies	30		
Financial Management & Resource Mobilization	20		
IQAC	30		
Total	100		
7	Innovations & Best Practices	Environmental Consciousness	30
		Innovations & Best Practices	40
		Total	100

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Dr. Veena Dani is Professor and Head of Psychology Department in Sarojini Naidu Govt. Girls Post Graduate College, Bhopal. She is also Co-coordinator of Quality Assurance Cell.

Dr. Dani has a passion for Applied Psychology, having accomplished 03 Major Research Projects on Development of self-esteem among adolescents and identification & intervention of dyslexia among school going children.

She has been a Resource Person at IIM Indore, RCVP Norhona Academy of Administration & Management, MP Bhoj Open University, etc.

Alzheimer's A Disease of the 21st Century

Dr. Veena Dani

Head, Department of Psychology

Alzheimer's disease is one of the six major threatening diseases of the 21st century. It is called threatening disease, as the symptoms disrupt normal day-to-day life of a patient. The most pathetic symptom of the disease is that the brain cells degenerate and die, which leads to memory loss, forgetfulness, mood changes, disorganization of thoughts and interest loss.

Many people with Alzheimer's also develop behavior and personality changes. These include restlessness, aggressiveness, disturbed sleep, social withdrawal, distrust in others, loss of inhibitions, delusions etc. There are six stages of this disease. However, the progression of symptoms varies from person to person. Majority of the patients suffering from this disease are above 65 years of age, although a few cases are also identified for less than 65 years of age.

SYMPTOMS

1. Memory Loss

The most striking symptom of this disease is memory loss, which interferes with daily routine. The patient may not be able to recall the name of person or place, loose keys, glasses around the house, gets lost in familiar places, forgets important date/ anniversary, etc. Memory loss is much more prominent for recent memory.

2. Visio-spatial Skills

There are problems in judging distance, navigating stairs and seeing objects in three dimensions. As a consequence, the patient is unable to form a proper image of the object present before him.

3. Concentration, Planning and Organization

The patient is unable to focus attention on the task on hand and following a particular

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sequence of task. He may face difficulties in making decision and solving problems.

4. Orientation

Severity of the symptoms takes place as the disease progresses. The patient can get disoriented for day, date, person and place. Sometimes, the patient is unable to recognize names of family members and identify them.

5. Thinking and reasoning

There is difficulty in thinking, especially, abstract thinking and logical reasoning. Gradually, inability to recognize and deal with numbers develops.

Soon, the patient is unable to manage his own finances.

6. Brain Shrinkage

Physician can make accurate diagnosis with the help of brain scan. Since, the brain cells degenerate and die, therefore, remaining brain cells, are fewer in number. This leads to brain shrinkage and fewer connections among surviving cells. MRI scan shows clumps of protein 'Beta-amyloid' (which interfere with cell to cell communication) and Tau protein which twists into abnormal tangles inside brain cells, which is responsible for decline and death of brain cells. As the disease progresses, the patient loses his control over urinary tract.

Who gets Alzheimer's disease?

Women are twice more prone to get this disease as compared to men. Scientists indicate a strong link with genetic inheritance. With a close relative (parent or sibling) who is diagnosed for Alzheimer's, the risk of developing this disease increases for the family members. People who had a history of head trauma are also vulnerable. When there is a decrease in brain Choline Acetyl Transferase (CAT). This decrease

correlates with cognitive impairment. Increased aluminum levels in brain areas are also found to be responsible for prominent neurofibrillary changes.

How to reduce the risk of Alzheimer's?

Engaging oneself in reading, writing, solving riddles, learning new/ foreign language and taking part in educational courses are beneficial; since, these lower the risk. Playing group sports, ground games (tennis, golf, etc.), swimming, walking and social interactions also help in prevention.

Interestingly, there are evidences which suggest that the same factors which put a person at risk for heart disease are contributory factors for Alzheimer's too. These are lack of exercise, smoking, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, diabetes, heavy weight etc.

Research evidences suggest that green leafy vegetable, nuts, berries, beans, whole grains, fish, poultry, olive oil and wine are beneficial and reduce risk. However, one should avoid red meat, butter, cheese, pastries & sweets, fried foods & fast food, as far as possible.

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Inclusive Education

Dr. Kala Mohan

Educational Management Consultant & Child Counselor

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

When every child is welcomed and valued regardless of ability or disability.

Inclusive Education is an attitude

It means the doors to schools, classrooms and school activities are open to every child and they are offered every opportunity to be included with their non-disabled peers.

The focus is on giving every child, the help he needs, to learn because all children can learn.

Inclusive Education is NOT:

Dumping kids with disabilities into general classrooms without the support & services they need to become successful.

Cutting back special education services as a “trade off” for being in the general education classroom.

Sacrificing the Education of kids without disabilities so kids with disabilities can be included.

Is Inclusive School, an Effective School ?

Inclusive Education is a guaranteed long term investment with high premium but assured returns.

Special Education is a sort of individualized supports that, give kids with disabilities, an extra help, they need to learn, from general curriculum. The various therapies, that can be offered, are:

- Physical therapy ;
- Speech therapy ;
- Language therapy ;
- Behavior plan ;
- Environmental accommodations ;
- Curriculum adaptations ; and
- Communication board.

Each student has an IEP. In India, do we have an IEP for each student with special need which includes ?

- learning goals & objectives for the year ;

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- the services and supports the student will receive ;
- accommodations for the student (different ways of learning or responding) ;
- if and to what extent, the general curriculum will be modified for the student ; and
- if and why the student will be out of the general education classroom and away from non-disabled students.

Students can't learn general curriculum unless they are in the room where it is being taught.

How do the IEP goals fit into the general curriculum?

Goals may be different but needs to be related (like learning to recognize a triangle when others are learning the angles in a triangle).

The student may need to be taught in a different way (like doing hands-on activities instead of listening to a lecture).

The student may need to work in a different way (like using a computer instead of pencil and paper).

Accommodation or Modification?

Accommodations are used when the student is expected to learn the same curricular content. But the student may be taught in a different way or need changes in the environment.

Modifications are used when the student is expected to learn less or different curricular content. This could require the modification of assignments, tests, worksheets and other materials in the classroom.

What are accommodations?

Accommodations are changes in teaching methods. It can include changes in :

- where you teach ;
- who teaches ;
- how you teach ;
- how the student can respond ; and
- materials to be used.

Know the Curriculum !

You have to know what you are trying to teach (curriculum) before you can change how you teach it.

If you make the wrong changes, you can end up teaching a different concept than the one you wanted the student to learn.

Room Accommodations

- Special chairs or cushions, lower or high table or chair, tilted desk top.
- Different or additional lighting (not fluorescent), sitting by a window for natural light.
- Sitting close to the blackboard or teacher, sitting away from others.
- Stand, instead of sitting or sitting instead of standing.
- Picture schedules, visual cues or visual

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timer.

- Quiet times or places to help concentration.
- Color coding.
- Visual organization of the room and supplies.
- Keeping materials for student and handing out as needed.
- Have at least part of the room bare with nothing on walls, ceilings or floors.

Teacher Accommodations

- Don't wear a lot of jewelry (distracts kids with ADHD).

- Don't wear cologne (hard on allergies).
- Count to 10 before letting anyone answer questions (processing time).
- Vary teaching methods.
- Projects for extra credit, in place of timed tests.
- Giving instructions one step at a time, instead of all at once.
- Ask questions to get replica of information.
- Divide the class (small groups, peer partners, peer tutors).
- Set up lessons (community instruction, role playing activities).
- Change the learning goals (more time, cooperate, share).
- Create alternative activity (learning center, research teams).
- Use a tape recorder for taking notes and giving reports.
- Give Sensory breaks.
- Use a touch screen, voice activated computer, switch controls or adapted keyboard, mouse, calculator.
- Peer tutoring or peer taking notes.
- Small group work instead of individual assignments.
- Assistance with organizing.
- More time to transition to next activity.
- Change the materials (counting actual objects, tape recorder).
- Find out how much or what kind of

Individual Accommodations

- Fewer problems on a page, large and dark print.
- Read things to students and give verbal tests.
- Communication device or sign language.

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personal assistance a student gets (prompts, verbal cues, gestures, physical assistance).

Modifying Grades

Use a grading system to show the combination of what they learned and how hard they tried.

Give extra credit for consistent efforts and completing assignments.

Give extra points for positive behaviors or extra assignments.

Base assignments and grades on meeting IEP goals.

- Reduce the amount of writing by using T/F, MCQs or fill in the blanks or oral tests.
- Give child less to learn at a time.
- Allow students to take classes as pass/fail.

Accommodations work !

Before

- Refused to do work ;
- Behavior outburst ;
- Unable to stay seated ;
- Yelled and hit other kids ;
- No friends ; and
- Refused many class activities.

After

- Does class work; learned difficult terms (like life span, germinate and organism) ;
- Almost no behavior problems ;
- Sits appropriately ;
- Loads of friends ; and
- Participates in all class activities.

LEARNING PEDAGOGICS

- 10% of what we read
- 20% of what we hear
- 30% of what we see
- 50% of what we both see and hear
- 70% of what is discussed
- 95% of what we teach someone else.

William Glasser

Graphics - Rishabh Garg DPS

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Dr. Shashi Rai has 50 years of Academic & Administrative experience in Higher Education.

She served as Professor of Botany and then as Principal in this College. She also worked in Directorate for Public Instructions for 5 years as Additional Director.

She has also been a Member, UGC (2006-2009) and Member, State Higher Education Council (RUSA).

She has visited many countries – Australia, Canada, USA; and attended NAFSA conference as leader of UGC delegation in June 2006.

Quality : Challenges & Sustenance

Dr. Shashi Rai

Member, State Higher Education Council, RUSA

PURPOSE OF EDUCATION

To produce academically competent, enlightened human resource with knowledge, information, skills & employability.

What is Quality ?

- Quality is a continuous process of development of an organization/ individual to achieve its preset targets, objectives and goals.
- The targets, objectives and goals need to be clearly drawn and written in unambiguous language, known to all.
- The process must be precise, meticulous and clearly directed, with measurable outcome.

Quality – A 3 pronged concept

- Preparatory phase of planning is followed by : Quality attainment; Quality enhancement; and Quality Sustenance.
- Should be taken as a Learning by doing concept.

- Dynamic, vibrant with scope for Change.
- Innovations, new ideas and need base strategies to be introduced from time to time.

Pre-requisites for Quality Attainment

- Each individual working in an institution must have conviction and commitment for quality.
- Individuals and the System, as a whole, should be quality conscious.
- Ample training programs, with outside experts, need to be organized through special focused modules.
- Tempo to be made and sustained throughout.

AREAS OF CONCERN & CHALLENGES

Planning

- Initial process of visualizing quality
- Areas to be identified like, Administration, Academics, Departments, Library, Sports,

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- A think tank should be developed from enthusiastic articulated teachers, non-teaching staff & stakeholders to take care of planning and monitoring.

Term Plan

- Long term plans with definite 4-5 years target ;
- Mid term plans with achievable 1-3 years target ; and
- Short term plans for immediate results within 6 months.

Governance from Vision to Implementation

- To create a vision and develop an understanding about the system at macro- and micro- level.
- To evolve appropriate execution mechanism.
- To put system in place with dimension of time and space.
- To set up an effective monitoring system.
- To ensure provision and optimal utilization of resources.
- To keep vigil on the quality of the system.
- To ascertain that due benefits are conveyed to the beneficiary i.e. student.

Pre-requisites of Good Governance

- Clarity of vision.
- Democratic instead of Autocratic approach (based on the principles of participation & transparency).
- Stake-holders be given due importance in planning, execution and feedback.
- Decentralization of powers with clearly defined responsibilities.
- High level of Accountability.

- Full proof monitoring mechanism with properly placed outcomes.
- Beneficiary centered approach.
- Guardianship to safe-guard quality culture and branding of the institution.

Academic Transactions

- Academic ambience.
- Availability of teaching – learning resources.
- Constant motivation and inspiration.
- Stringent monitoring of academic schedules.

- Repeated review meetings.

- FDP as an in-built mechanism.

- Regular feedback system.

SUSTENANCE

- Quality to be made a habit of life.
- The tempo for quality should not die.
- Quality must be nurtured as a valued icon of the institution.

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Mr. I.S. Dani has been Additional Chief Secretary in Home, Medical Education Departments, Govt. of MP. He has also served as Principal Secretary in the Departments of Agriculture, Panchayat & Rural Development, Health & Family Welfare, School Education, Science & Technology and retired as Director General RCVP Naronha Academy of Administration and Management, Bhopal.

Mr. Dani, an engineering graduate from Jabalpur University, had done his Masters in Social Sciences from Burmingham University, UK. He has translated a book, Ek Anari Ki Kahi Kahani.

Striving for Excellence

Indraneel Shankar Dani

Former Additional Chief Secretary, Madhya Pradesh

- Excellence is something that brings joy.
- All, in their deep, wants to excel.
- But, over a period of time, people develop an attitude - everything goes on.
- To achieve **excellence**, create a passion. To create a passion, one should Dream and the Dream should always be beyond your approach.
- To find **passion**, there are three ways :

There are 4 myths regarding excellence :

Myth # 1

Those who achieve excellence are born with extraordinary abilities.

Myth # 2

You need to get favorable opportunity or chance to excel.

Myth # 3

Excellence means something on a grand, spectacular and a huge scale.

Myth # 4

It demands too much time.

Myth # 5

The system is rotten. I alone cannot change it.

- * Find out deeper meaning of your work ;
- * Then create an urge to challenge yourself; and
- * Find out a way to produce passion.

• Once you are filled with passion you are on the way to excellence.

• To achieve excellence one has to analyze his Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities & Challenges (SWOC) and make STRATEGY :

- * Plan ;
- * Goals ;
- * Mission ; and
- * Vision.

• Implementation through team building, resource allocation, monitoring and

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review mechanism, corrective actions and preventive actions.

- Venture upon creativity, Ideas & innovations.

Barriers in creativity

- Self imposed barriers ;
- Patterns or one unique answer ;
- Conformity ;
- Not challenging the obvious ;
- Evaluating too quickly ; and
- Fear of looking like a fool.

Recapitulation

- Everybody can pursue excellence - here and now.
- Pursuit excellence is a matter of attitude - and soon becomes a habit.
- You can acquire passion - even if you are not born with it, or haven't acquired it so far.
- You need to dream to make your life meaningful - and believe in it.
- SWOC can help you strategize.
- There is no substitute for hard work.
- Creativity and innovation help you to break mental barriers - and make work a play.

Departing Questions

- What are our dreams?
- What should we do to become more passionate about realizing our dreams?
- How do we harness our strengths, overcome our weaknesses, create new opportunities, and neutralize potential threats to realize our dreams?

- How can we bring innovation in our work?
- How do we teach our students to do all of the above?

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Quest for Peace & Happiness

Rajesh Jagesiya

Trainer cum Facilitator, The Art of Living, Bengaluru

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Mr. Rajesh Jagesiya completed his graduation in Electronic Engineering from the University of Mumbai. He served in a Canadian software company for 8 years.

Then, he quit the job and joined Art of Living as Trainer cum Facilitator. He has visited Canada, South Korea, America and Germany.

POINTS TO PONDER

- Why we always need someone to keep us happy ?
 - How to make us strong in a sense that no negativity can poke into our mind ?
 - We doubt all those who talk nice about us. How to handle doubts ?
 - How to increase happiness within us and learn that happiness does not depend on materialistic things ?
 - How to try and revive the child within us and learn to be a complete yogi ?
- life is "breath." Breathing in and breathing out helps us to quiet ourselves
- When we breathe properly, the out-going air releases negative vibes and the fresh in-coming oxygen comes in with positive energy.
 - Give-up all your negative thoughts and revive yourself like a child who looks at everything with joy. A mind without agitation (or a mind with relaxation) is meditation.
 - A 15 minute dhyana a day is capable of keeping us happy for a complete day

PLAUSIBLE ANSWERS

- Retuning to yogi, nature will help us to achieve happiness from inside.
- If we decide not to think about a particular incident, we keep on thinking about it. So we need to control our mind.
- Sri-Sri Ravishankar speaks, the most important thing that we have missed in

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Mrs. Amita Singh is a Dietician & Nutrition Expert

She started her career from Chandigarh in 1980. On coming back to Madhya Pradesh, she started the first private dietetics clinic. She is consultant to National Hospital, Raj Bhavan and Department of Women & Child Welfare.

She also conducts workshops and writes on Nutrition.

Balanced Diet

Mrs. Amita Singh

Consultant, Nutrition & Dietetics

FUNCTIONS OF FOOD

- Meals are influenced by social, physical, economic factors.
- Carbohydrates, Fats, Proteins have different roles to play.
- Energy is provided by carbohydrates, Fats, Proteins.
- Proteins repair body.
- Diet with fruits and vegetables increase immunity to fight with diseases.
- Take handful of joar, bajra, makka, raagi, and maize flour. Add 2 bowls of gram, 4 bowls of wheat flour and roasted linseed. Knead all, into a dough and make its Paratha with ghee.
- One should take 40 gms of assorted dry fruits - groundnuts, almonds, cashew nuts, pistachios, raisins, figs etc.
- To avoid hypothyroidism, do not take raw foods like radish, turnips, groundnuts cabbage, etc.

Food Tips

- Use cereals (joar, bajra, rice, maize, wheat).
- Discourage use of white flour biscuits. rather take chick-peas and kidney beans.
- Use 1 kg. gram flour and mix with 4 kg. wheat flour.
- Consume Dal twice a week. Have amla, unripe green chilli.
- Use traditional oils like groundnut and mustard oil. Coconut oil, being the best for hair & skin.
- Drink adequate water. Avoid fresh juices, instead have the fruits directly.
- Consume vinegar, black pepper, ginger, onion, garlic, turmeric for prevention of Alzheimer's.
- Avoid fried foods, rely on idli, chick-peas chat, dhokla, sandwich, veg-cutlet, etc.

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Dr. Moni Mathur has been Deputy Secretary and In-charge of State Quality Assurance Cell in Department of Higher Education, Govt. of MP. She served the department for 34 years as Professor of Botany.

She has also been Advisor to the Dept of Biotechnology, MP Biotechnology Council and Member NAAC Peer Team.

Perspectives & Prospects in Green Research

Dr. Moni Mathur

Former Advisor, MP Biotechnology Council

A Century of Extremes

- More than 6 billion people.
- Sustained by primary production :
 - * Capital of life ; and
 - * Green wealth.

Technology at your Doorstep

- Genetically Modified Crops.
- GM Humans..
- Machines with Artificial intelligence.
- Super Powerful Computers and Gadgets.
- Man directing his own evolution.

Earth Scenario

- CO₂ emission has increased 12 times.
- Coal, Oil, Natural gas by 4 times.
- Use of energy has increased 70%.
- Water has become scarce.

Scenario - 2040

- Gordon Moore of Intel (1956) predicted number of transistors on a chip would double in every 15 years.
- 10 doublings thousand 1971
- 20 doublings million 1986
- 30 doublings billion 2001
- 40 doublings trillion 2017
- Pietà and zeta comps

World Stress for Natural Resources

- Shortage of Oil, Uranium.
- Water scarcity.
- Not enough food.
- Scarcity of arable land.
- Global warming
- Carbon trading.
- People 'll wear masks & astronaut clothes as CO₂ emissions would be high.

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Nature- The Sole Provider

Earth has regenerative Capacity

The Road Ahead

- Energy Audit ;
 - * Non Conventional ;
 - * Solar - Institution, Home; and
 - * Wind .
- Water Audit :
 - * Conserve ;
 - * Quality ;
 - * Pragmatic use ; and
 - * Recycle (Netherland roads designed to absorb rain water).
- Bio-resource Audit :
 - * Endangered species ; and
 - * Balance between consumer producer.
- Waste Audit :
 - * Methods to recycle.

Industry can be green

- Research on fuel cells.
- Clean engines & machines.
- Use Nanotechnology .

- Carpet Industry in US : Provide carpet on lease & take back to recycle.
- Devise ways for each unit in its own way (Extended Producer Responsibility).
- In GE – emission standards tougher than Kyoto targets.
- Solar and wind driven machines.
- Solar Cars.

Eco Affluent Society

- Technology in Harmony with nature, like the semi-conservative DNA.
- Convergence of life with technology has emerged as a Panacea.
- Promote “green genes”

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Making Money with Joy

Pradeep Karambelkar

Investment Advisor

Why is investment important for female?

- Because an average female lives longer than male;
- Secondly, one needs more money in old age.
- Further, it makes them independent.

- different asset locations. Trading could be injurious to financial health.
- Equity is risky, better buy good companies and give sufficient time.
- In next 5 years, 9 lakh crore will come into the Indian market and if one invests today in domestic market, it will definitely pay him rich dividends.

Where to invest your hard earned money ?

It's often difficult to decide on long term or short term investment to maintain its value against a declining value of rupee.

There are two sectors for investment : one for tax saving viz. PPF or Insurance; and another, tax free bonds & equities.

Before investing into equities, or tax saving schemes, it is necessary to keep rate of inflation in mind.

Again, wealth saving is more important than wealth making.

- Shares and trading - sell and buy on daily basis. Investment should be done in

- Go to SIP (Systemic Investment Plan).
- Make regular and long term investments.
- Invest in different asset locations.

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Investments : Pros & Cons

L.D. Pandit

Ex Manager, MP Cooperative Bank

Investment ?

Facts & Figures

Female are the best investors and conservators in our country.

Higher GDP \geq 7.5 growth will open opportunities for investment and income of the common man in :

1. Money Market : Government schemes/ Bank deposits/ Financial institutions ;
2. Capital market : Shares & Debentures ;
3. Credit market : Short & long term investment.

Advice to All

- Diversified saving is sensible in different companies.

For secured investments :

- Never invest in Non-Banking finance companies.
- Never follow or copy others for investment.

- Invest through your own judgment.
- Start 10-30% saving from today :
 - * 30th age - 10% saving of income ;
 - * 50th age - 30% saving of income.
- Prefer Fixed Deposits because of liquidity in funds and avoid savings in Mutual funds and Equity.
- Keep at least 5% fund as Fixed Deposits or cash for emergencies.
- Think twice before making investment in gold
- Always pay taxes/ lease rent on investment in Real estate.
- Don't transfer hard earned money to your spouse or children during the tenure of your life or before death.
- Retirement plan - Don't mortgage your property for any guarantee, bail to anybody.

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Self Appraisal for PBAS & CAS

Dr. Bharti Jain

Professor, Department of Chemistry

Dr. Bharti Jain has been a Professor of Chemistry for 30 years. She has guided 12 scholars for the Ph.D. degree of the university and has published 45 research papers.

She has served the College as Administrative Officer, Controller (Examination Cell) and as Subject Expert in Govt. Women's Polytechnic College, Bhopal.

She has been a regular speaker at RCVP Noronha Academy of Administration & Management.

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The quality of education is facing threat in our country in terms of responsibility, accountability and increased expectations by the stakeholders. Incorporating sustainability in Higher education institutes are not only advantageous for themselves but also for the sustainability of the entire nation.

To maintain the quality, based on standards in higher education and to make the selection procedure for recruitment & promotions under the career advancement Scheme (CAS) in universities and colleges, UGC had established regulations for the teachers in higher education institutions in year 1956, which were further revised from time to time.

As sixth pay came into reality in 2010, the University Grants Commission introduced a Performance Based Appraisal System (PBAS), based on weightages given to the

performance of the candidate in different fields, to make selection procedure more transparent, objective & credible and for the maintenance of Standards in Higher education. In the present system, it is mandatory for all universities and colleges to prepare Performance Based Appraisal Report in the prescribed format, as suggested by the UGC, mentioning the Academic Performance Indicators (API) on the grounds of merits & credentials submitted by the applicant teacher.

API scores are used for screening purpose only and have no bearing on expert assessment of candidates in Direct Recruitment or CAS.

In Madhya Pradesh, the Department of Higher education has applied the scheme for all higher education institutes, since 2012-2013.

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Self-appraisal helps to figure out teacher's strengths and weaknesses. The scoring is done under the three broad categories :

- Teaching, learning & evaluation related activities ;
- Co-curricular, extension & professional development related activities ; and
- Research & academic contributions.

The API indicators suggest that most emphasis is given on teaching and

learning. Teaching and examination related duties are compulsory for the teachers and they need to score a minimum of 75 points per year. Co-curricular, extensions and professional development activities are not mandatory and teacher can score a minimum of 15 points from a wide variety of activities. In the third category, a teacher can score as much points he/she likes to.

The third category of UGC regulations is related with various aspects of research and academic contribution of teachers. Research paper writing, publication of books, projects of different kinds, guidance to Ph.D. & M.Phil. students and different kinds of trainings, workshops, conferences & seminars, invited lectures are the parameters in which a teacher needs to score points. UGC regulations elucidate that at different stages, the teachers need to score points accordingly.

The score required for the teachers from stage I to II, II to III, III to IV and IV to V are 5, 10, 15 and 20 per academic year and 20, 50, 45 and 45 per assessment period

respectively.

It is quite evident from the above discussion that there is a need of slight modification in the points scored in category II and to make the teachers more focused towards the teaching and research.

The regulations are made for the betterment of students and teachers. The major role of a teachers is to impart skills, knowledge, compatibility and to make the student good human being. It could be achieved through applying multi-dimensional approach towards the maintenance of standards and quality in higher education which will lead towards the better performance of students, society and in turn, country.

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